
**UNENDING CULTURAL AND ECONOMIC
COLONISATION: THE CASE OF ALU KURUMBA
ADIVASI WOMEN**

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***Abstract:** Recorded history reveals that the adivasis of India have been facing marginalization for the last few centuries. They have been losing their control over forest resources and the integration policies of the state have been unfruitful since independence from British colonisation. Alu Kurumba is one of the particularly vulnerable tribal groups living in the Nilgiris district of Tamil Nadu, India. This community has been facing cultural and economic colonisation in the form of restricting their rights towards forest resources and lack of alternate livelihood apart from employment in plantations. This dual marginalisation impacts Alu Kurumba women severely. This paper is an outcome of a descriptive research that used a post-positivism framework. The researcher selected 50 Alu Kurumba women from seven hamlets for this research. The sampling techniques were snowball and convenient. About 82 per cent of the respondents' families were in the category of Low Standard of Living Index.*

***Keywords:** Adivasis, Alu Kurumbas, forest policies, colonisation, tea and coffee plantations.*

Introduction

In the current neo-liberal development paradigm of the state, there are those who do not find a space - such as eco-systems and adivasi communities (also called tribals or indigenous people). For the last two centuries, the adivasis of India have been suffering numerous injustice at the hands of the dominant society (Shah, 2005). The policies of the state towards forests over the years and their implementation have made it difficult for the adivasis, especially Adivasi women, to access their rights and development. The policies focusing on raising the productivity of the forest lands in

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the form of plantations, social forestry, and wasteland development programmes have made forests a commercial production hub and have ignored the perspectives of adivasis (Venkateswaran, 1995).

Likewise, the cultural values of adivasis have been side-lined with the introduction of modern and monopolising technologies. For example, the lives and livelihoods of the adivasis of the Nilgiris district, Tamil Nadu, like Kurumba, Kota, Irula, Paniya, and Toda are affected by the uncritical intrusion of the dominant society (Reddy & Rao, 2003). Until British colonisation in 1823, the adivasis of Nilgiris were cut off from the Indian rulers and their misery increased exponentially after British infiltration (Bird, 1987, cited by Saravanan, 2006). During the British rule, adivasi cultivators became plantation labourers due to enforcement of plantation industry, declaration of reserved forest, non-adivasi settlements, and ineffective policies causing the alienation of adivasi lands (Kumar, 1965, cited by Saravanan, 2006).

Observation by Kapp and Hocking (1989, cited by Parthasarathy, 2000) stated that Kurumba was the first adivasi community in Nilgiris to become known to the research scholars but they were the last to be studied closely. Alu Kurumbas, the respondents of this research, are one among the five subgroups of Kurumbas living in the Nilgiris district.

Rasaily (2007) stressed that women workers form the backbone of the tea economy. In Tamil Nadu, women workers in plantation comprise more than 90 per cent of all labourers. In this scenariotaking into account the conditions of this workforce, Singh (2001) elucidated that the role of women in tea plantations (in North East India) has not undergone much improvement inspite of elaborate welfare measures by the state. They continue to be exploited in the highly male dominated social and functional milieu of tea and coffee plantations. The conditions remain same in South India. For example, an article in the Financial Express (2002) stated that the plight of tea estate workers, especially women, in Kerala

had become alarming due to high reduction in tea prices and closing down of tea estates.

In this flow of narrative, the recent protest by the women workers of Kannan Devan Hills Plantations Limited in Munnar, Kerala, and their achievement is an exception. That protest could be a new beginning for women workers of the plantations to organize under a new banner instead of aligning with any trade unions or political parties (Philip, 2015). On hindsight, the researcher thinks that it would be very difficult for the women workers in Kotagiri (area of the research) to organise a similar protest against the plantation owners considering reasons such as the fragmentation of plantations and their marginalised identities.

According to 1991 Population Census of India, the total population of Alu Kurumbas was 5000 in Nilgiris district (Scialabba & Hattam, 2002). They are settled in 20 adivasi hamlets in Kotagiri block of Nilgiris district and most of them are working in tea and coffee plantations (Parthasarathy, 2000). Of these 20 hamlets, the respondents for this research were selected from seven hamlets namely Andiyari, Banagudi, Baviyoor, Kallur, Sellari, Semancherry, and Vellarikombai.

This article concurrently analyses the impact of forest policies on one side and the conditions of the Alu Kurumba women employed in the tea and coffee plantations on the other. This portrayal helps establish the marginalisation of Adivasis in both cultural and economic spheres. The analysis of empirical data obtained from the respondents (the total number of respondents for this research was 50 Alu Kurumba women) revealed a disheartening fact that no single respondent has got permanency in their jobs and estate owners did not promote any casual workers as permanent employees owing to cost and various other reasons. Similarly, none of the respondents were aware of the Plantation Labours Act, 1951, which protects the welfare of the plantation workers.

Methodology

The theoretical position of this research is post-positivism. Adam (2014, cf. Hetherington, 2000), while describing post-positivism, states that “it is neither anti-positivism nor a continuation of positivism by other means.” It negates the strict positivist aspects and believes that “... the quantification and use of sophisticated statistical methods and mathematical models do not enable the attainment of scientifically relevant insights (about reality)” And it advocates for a complex research design “... such as triangulation or the integration of methods, and further meta-analyses and other combinations of quantitative and qualitative methods based on emphasising the context and specifics of the cases ...”

Trochim (2006) in continuation, revealed that individuals (or researchers who use positivism) cannot see the world “as it really is” and bias is inherent in any research. Hence, in postpositivism “... to improve the objectivity of what we do is to do it within the context of a broader contentious community of truth-seekers who criticize each other's work.”

The data for this research was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected from the Alu Kurumba women and the secondary sources were books, research publications, articles, and newspaper reports.

The researcher used triangulation method in this research. The interview schedule was used for assessing the conditions of Alu Kurumba women workers and the content analysis was used for contextual understanding of forest policies and status of tea plantation workers.

Of the 123 Alu Kurumba families from the above mentioned seven villages, 50 families were selected for this research. The researcher selected a woman member who works in plantations from each of these families and interviewed her with the help of a local civil society, *Nilgiris District Adivasi Samooga Munnetra Sangam*.

Being an outsider and a male, the researcher faced issues in asking some sensitive questions to the respondents. A member of the above said agency, accompanied the researcher to all the seven villages. The presence of this member during the interview helped the researcher navigate these difficulties.

In order to select the villages, the researcher used lottery method (random sampling method). Similarly, to select the respondents from seven villages, snowball and convenient sampling techniques (non-random sampling method) were followed since not all the families in these villages were working in tea and coffee plantations and not all were available during the researcher's visit. The data was collected between April 2009 and June 2009.

Forest Policies

Forest communities such as Adivasis have been subjugated to a progressive loss of control over their natural resource base by both the colonial and the post-colonial states. Although the interests behind the formation and execution of state forest policies may have differed, the methods used have been strikingly similar in both these periods (Guha, 1983). This section briefly sketches the imperialistic attitude of the forest policies at various junctions.

Definition: According to the Indian Forest Act, 1972, the legal extent of forests depends upon the process of notification. Similarly, the Supreme Court of India in one of the judgements noted that anything should be forest if it meets one or both of these two definitions: either the lexical dictionary definition or land recorded as forest on any government record. These ways of interpretation help the government use its draconian powers to mark an area as forest or non-forest (DNA, 2011).

Pre-colonial India: About 1000 years ago, 80 per cent of the land in the Indian subcontinent was estimated to possess healthy forest cover (Poffenberger, 1996). The protection and management of the environment started in the early stages of human history. It is

believed that people lived in close harmony with nature. Human beings worshipped different elements of nature such as trees, forest, animals, rivers, and mountains (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

Consequently, many pre-colonial dynasties promoted extensive cultivation which resulted in shrinking of forests. While most of the dynasties below the Himalayas, ancient and medieval, claimed ownership of all resources, they in practice left the local communities largely in control of these resources (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

In the Adivasi society, the ecological niches were self-contained systems of resource use in the form of the hunting-gathering economies and shifting cultivation. These practices were not so harmful to the ecology because their resource use was based on the limited needs of the small populations and highly regulative socio cultural practices (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

Colonial Rule: After the British invasion in 1600, their early days of rule were days of plunder of natural resources. Commercial use increasingly dominated forestry objectives and practices. By around 1860, they intensified deforestation to draw timber for ship building, iron-smelting, and farming. In India, the process greatly intensified after the building of the railway networks in 1853 (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

In 1865, the British government first enacted the Forest Act and it was revised after 13 years. The Act extended to most of the territories and facilitated the acquisition of the forest areas earmarked for railway supplies. In succession, they came up with the first Forest Policy in 1884, which came into implementation through the Forest Act of 1927 (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

The prime impact of colonial forestry was felt in the breakup of

traditional village economies and stable well-adjusted systems of resource use. The forests promoted monoculture like plantations and excluded the rights of the people from forests. They used the forests as a production house to extract the maximum amount of revenue and meet the goals of imperialism (Chaudhuri & Bandopadhyay, 2004).

Post-Independence: Despite the change in power from colonial to independent India, forest resource management changed little: exclusionary processes accelerated as successive Indian governments strove to consolidate state authority over forest resources and increasingly bind their exploitation to state goals and interests (Haeuber, 1993).

The first post-independence statement of the Indian forest policy was issued as a Government of India resolution in 1952. The new national policy leaned heavily on the 1894 Forest Policy Resolution as its point of reference. According to the 1952 resolution, village communities in the neighbourhood of a forest will naturally make a greater use of its products for the satisfaction of their domestic and agriculture needs (Kannan, 1980, cited by Haeuber, 1993). The policymakers acknowledged that forests should be open for grazing and fodder collection, as long as these practices did not become harmful to the forests and national interests. And in order to fulfil these diverse roles the 1952 resolution called for a classification of forest resources nearly identical to that contained in the 1894 policy. The area controlled by forest departments was divided into protection forests, national forests, village forests (instead of minor forests) and treelands (the category of pasturelands was eliminated). Protection forests remained dedicated to maintenance of areas susceptible to erosion and degradation. National forests were earmarked for commercial timber supplies. Village forests and treelands were intended to supply fuel-wood, timber and fodder needs of the rural people (Haeuber, 1993).

Contrary to the points on paper, the Scheduled Areas and

Scheduled Tribes Commission observed in April 1960 that the traditional rights of indigenous forest-dwellers were being increasingly curtailed after the 1952 policy enactment (Haeuber, 1993).

On the other hand, the central government curtailed the responsibility of the state governments by enacting the 42nd Constitutional Amendment in 1976. This was necessary because the state government had ample powers to de-reserve any forest and it led to many forests disappearing. Increasing deforestation and ecological imbalance had led the central government to pass the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980. It restricts the use of any forest for a non-forest purpose, without permission of the central government. However, states have been given a free hand to conduct any activities for the conservation and development of forests and the wildlife (Haeuber, 1993).

Around the same period, the government began a new programme called Social Forestry with the primary objective of providing fuel woods for domestic users. The scheme failed miserably since the farmers were interested in selling the timber to industries and manufacturers to increase their cash income rather than using it for domestic purposes. Then the government came up with a new Indian Forest Policy, 1988, to ensure environmental stability and maintenance of ecological balance. This policy gave too little importance to the needs of adivasis and other local forest dwellers. To overcome this problem, the Joint Forest Management Programme was launched and people were included as partners in the administration of forests rather than as a harmful element who have to be controlled and excluded. The rights of the people were still limited to the extent that the state allowed (Haeuber, 1993).

The consecutive contrasting policies and orders made forest administration difficult. The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980 vests great amounts of power in the Central government, while at the same time, the National Forest Policy, 1988 tries to give the locals

more power in forest management in line with the 73rd and 74th amendments. Likewise, there are various competing interests with respect to forests, which include wildlife lovers, industrialists, rural activists, and the foresters themselves. In addition, the administrators have, either at their own behest or due to political pressure, consistently put the interests of the industrial community over ecological integrity and the local communities (Better Legal Research, 2010).

The Scheduled Tribes and other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006 was enacted after a hard-fought and prolonged struggle of adivasis, other forest dwellers, and activists. Some of the aspects of this Act are recognition of the rights of non-tribal traditional forest dwellers; recognising the rights of tribal and traditional forest dwellers in areas declared as protected areas; revised process for identification of such protected areas to ensure a more transparent process; and increased ceiling of 2.5 hectares of land to 4 hectares. Most importantly, it prescribed that no diversion of forest land would happen without the consent of the *gram sabha* (Ghosh, 2006).

There is a wide variation in how the Forest Rights Act, 2006 is being implemented in different states, as would be expected with such a complex legislation. For example, Chhattisgarh has formed Forest Rights Committees throughout the state, whereas in Tamil Nadu there were no initiatives at all. In 2008, the government of Tamil Nadu reported that they would not act in the absence of direct instructions from the centre. Similarly, the Ministry of Environment and Forests is spreading the false propaganda that the rights afforded in the Act would not be recognised in the tiger habitats (Campaign for Survival and Dignity, 2008).

The other sphere of this research is the status of the Alu Kurumba tea estate workers. Of the seven villages selected for this research, two villages were part of estate houses and remaining were organic hamlets. The owners of the former hamlets were the estate owners.

Status of the Alu Kurumba Women

Rasaily (2007) had stated in his work that tea estate workers were subjected to overwork, bondage, inclement weather and gross violation of labour and human rights for almost a century. He further stressed that there was no organised form of resistance, that the development of trade union consciousness and organisation among the tea plantation workers was comparatively a delayed phenomenon.

Trade Union and Wages: From the view of the researcher, a similar situation still prevails with the Alu Kurumba women employed in the tea estates of Nilgiris. The trade union consciousness has not reached them yet. The outcome of the empirical analysis showed that only four out of the 50 respondents were part of trade unions. Nearly 66 per cent of them work based on targets in plucking tea leaves every day, and supervisors mock them if they were unable to reach those targets.

India has passed the Plantation Labours Act, 1951 for the welfare of plantation workers, and it was amended on various occasions based on the progress of the plantation industry. This act protects the rights of the workers and includes work place, housing, working method, timing, wages, maternity care, health benefits, and education benefits. The state government is responsible for the effective administration and implementation of this Act (Mukherjee, 2003). However, this Act is not implemented properly in the field - tea plantation workers are still paid wages below the minimum wage of agricultural workers (Lahiri, 2000).

Table 1 – Daily wages of the respondents

Daily wage	Frequency	Percent
Rs. 50 to 70	14	28
Rs. 71 to 109	26	52
Rs. 110 and more	10	20
Total	50	100

The respondents revealed that more than half (54%) of them were receiving daily wages based on the kilograms of tea leaves that they pluck every day. For a kilogram of tea leaves they were paid between one and two rupees. On an average, a worker was able to pluck 35 to 40 kilograms of tea leaves per day. On the contrary, the Plantation Labours Act states that each plantation worker should receive a minimum wage of Rs. 110 per day for eight hours of work. Only ten individuals among these 50 respondents were receiving wages more than Rs. 110. Table 2 explains this in detail.

Table 2 – Wages classification and income

Wages	Classification of respondents daily income			Total
	Rs. 50 to 70	Rs. 71 to 109	Rs. 110 and more	
Not based on Kilograms	4	12	7	23
Based on Kilograms	10	14	3	27
Total	14	26	10	50

Access to Health Care: The working condition of women in the informal sector is pathetic. They work both at home and outside. They collect firewood and water, cook food, care for their children and ailing parents, and satisfy the needs of their husbands. After attending to all these unpaid works, she goes out to be abused, exploited, and gets a pittance as wages (Menon, 2003). About 84 per cent of the participants shared that supervisors purposely reduce the quantity of the tea leaves plucked because of ulterior motives. Similarly, a majority (90%) of them felt that their working environment was not safe even during the day.

Table 3 – Distance to Primary Health Care Centres (PHC)

PHC	Mean	S.D.	Minimum	Maximum
Distance in Kilometres	5.06	2.01	2	9

Nearly 60 per cent of them had to travel five to seven kilometres to access the primary health care facility. The average distance to the PHC was five kilometres and the maximum distance was nine kilometres. The Plantation Labours Act in contrast has asked employers to set up a health care sub-centre in their respective plantations for emergency needs. In this circumstance, more than half (52%) of the participants divulged that they had come across accidents in their working sites. Many of the plantations (these 50 participants were from 17 different estates) that the researcher studied are situated on steep slopes with no proper pathways. The workers have to balance a heavy head load while plucking leaves and carry it to the weighing spots. Also, as the age of the women workers increases, they may not have enough strength to carry the load. Of the total respondents, there were only two respondents who were above 40 years of age and still continuing their employment in plantations.

Working Hours and Income: In this scenario, globalisation and market dependency of cash crops like tea have added to the difficulties of marginalised communities. The stagnancy of tea prices since quite some time and overall price increase of essential commodities owing to the inflationary policies of the central government have worsened the situation of the workers (Bandhu, 2010).

Of the total respondents, 66 per cent shared that they were under constant pressure by the supervisors to work more than eight hours. Of those who did so, nearly half (42%) did not receive any additional income.

Figure 1 – Family income of the respondents (in Rupees)

The above figure1 shows that slightly more than two-fifth of the respondents (44%) had family income between Rs. 2500 and Rs. 4000, 22 per cent had family income between Rs. 1000 and Rs. 2500 while slightly less than one fifth of them (18%) had family income above Rs. 5500.

Figure 2 – Standard of Living Index (SLI) (in per cent)

This eight variable scale was formulated by Roy, Jayachandran and Banerjee (1999). The score ranges from zero to forty-eight. The variables tested in this scale includes separate room for cooking, type of house, source of lighting, fuel for cooking, source of drinking water, toilet facility, ownership of livestock, and ownership of goods. From the results, if the score of a family is between zero and nine then they will fall in the category of “Low SLI”, if the score is between 10 and 19, then they will be in the category of “Medium SLI” and 20 and above are families with “High SLI”.

Figure 2 divulges that more than four-fifth of the families (82%) of the respondents fall in the category of “Low SLI” and there were no families in the category of “High SLI”. A meagre 18 per cent of the families were in the group of “Medium SLI”.

The Labour Bureau (1981, cited by George, 2002) study examined the problems faced by women workers in the plantation sector. The outcomes elucidated that women were as skilful as men and in some cases, more competent. However, lack of formal education and training deprived them of skilled and supervisory jobs. Similarly, the prejudices of the employers prevented them being appointed as supervisors as it was feared that women would not be able to exercise proper control over the workmen. The situation resembles the one in Nilgiris. Alu Kurumba women workers stated that all their supervisors were male. The lack of alternative employment opportunities and curtailed access to minor forest produce by forest officials kept them trapped in the vicious cycle of endemic poverty.

Another study by Singh (cited by George, 2002) on women plantation workers of Tamil Nadu stated that the method of recruiting and organising labour in the plantation sector created a hierarchical and patriarchal structure characterised by semi-feudal attitudes towards workers, especially women workers. As these attitudes are retained and promoted, women come to be considered inferior to men in supervisory and managerial functions.

The respondents elucidated that about 52 per cent of them did not get maternity leave and the employers typically follow hire and fire methods. Nearly 26 per cent of the women workers faced physical assaults from their male supervisors. In accretion, George's (2002) study also showed that there were incidences where women in the tea estates were treated inhumanly such as sexual exploitation by their supervisors and superiors.

The data given by the respondents showed that none of the tea estates implemented the Vishakha judgement, 1999 (or the guidelines as per the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace – Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal, Act, 2013) and supervisors exploited the women workers - sometimes by compulsion and occasionally by using tactics like assigning hard work, placing them far away from call points, placing them alone in tea fields, and offering them attractive options like work permanency and crèche ayah appointments. They shared that sexual violence against women workers was prevalent in tea estates and information about this violence was not revealed in public owing to reasons like fear, stigma, and anxiety.

Conclusion

The Alu Kurumba women have been deprived of access to minor forest produce owing to the existing forest policies as well as poor working condition of the tea plantation sector. This perpetuates their endemic poverty and erodes their traditional social and economic subsistence.

Prabhu (1998) in his work condemned that today the state has emerged as the single largest alienator of the lands and other survival resources of adivasis. The provisions of regulations concerning alienation of adivasi land are not applied with respect to land acquired by the public sector projects and credit cooperatives. For adivasis, the forest occupies a central position in their culture and economy. The neo liberal policies of the government acquire their lands and erode their social and economic wellbeing.

In adivasi society, women contribute to the work force in a more substantial way than in non-Adivasi society. The ratio between male and female workers in the general population is 5:1, but among the adivasis it is 3:1. The freedom enjoyed by the Adivasi women in their own social system has been grossly misunderstood by dominant society and the local non-adivasis exploit adivasi women for their economic gain. This economic exploitation unavoidably paves way for physical and sexual exploitation (Prasad, 1988).

Participative management could be introduced in tea plantations to reduce exploitation and improve working conditions (Nair, 2007). However, if participative management is introduced, the workers may lose their rights under the Plantation Labour Act, 1951.

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